

Effect of Chief Executive officer (CEO) Dynamism on Firm Value of Listed Commercial Banks Evidence from Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the effect of Chief Executive Officer (CEO) dynamics on firm value of listed commercial bank in Nigeria. The study adopted ex-post facto research design and used secondary data collected from ten years audited annual accounts of 16 listed commercial banks. The dependent variable for the study is earning per share, while CEO ownership, CEO gender diversity and CEO reputation are used for the independent variables. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and regression analysis. The findings revealed a positive and significant influence of CEO ownership on value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This implies that having more ownership interest by the bank CEO adds value to the banks and brings about positive effect on the performance. The regression results revealed a positive statistically significant relationship between CEO gender diversity and value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria for the period investigated. This means that an increase in the numbers of women CEO of banks improves their value and hence the level of financial performance. This result may imply that increasing the number of female CEO could increase the board's monitoring since women are more inquisitive than male director. Board reputation has a positive but insignificant impact on value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria which implies that more numbers of CEO with national honor enhances the value of the banks and hence increases their financial performance insignificantly. It is therefore recommended that in order to boost and ensure continuous improvement of earnings of commercial banks in Nigeria. The board should ensure that the management cut across people with national honors. Furthermore, appointment of women to the banks board should be part of the cardinal point to be considered during appointment of CEO of banks.

Keywords CEO Dynamics; Firm Value; CEO Reputation; CEO Ownership

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Introduction

The position of the chief executive officer (CEO) has occupied many discussions in accounting and finance literatures in recent times. Corporate entities world-wide requires growth and development in a bid to attract funding from investors and potential investors. These investors, before they invest in a particular business organization, they often want to be sure that the business in which they are investing money is financially stable, economically viable, secured and have ability to generate the expected returns on their investment (Milan, 2007). According to Lai and Semiu (2012), corporate governance failure creates problems that could negatively influence investors' funds and consequently deteriorate the stability of the companies.

The CEO is one of the critical players in the corporate institutions. The CEOs occupied top positions of the management teams in firms, CEOs are able to guide the firms to actively pursue opportunities and control the structures and strategies of the firms (Altarawneh, et al., 2020). The success or failure of a firm is largely dependent on the leadership and majorly the CEO. Recent involvement and indictment of CEOs in financial statement and scandals has become a concern. For instance, in the United States, the CEO of Tyco, Kozlowski, manipulated earnings which resulted in the loss of US\$100 billion in the firms' market value (a sum that exceeded Enron's total loss) (Troy, et al, 2011). Most importantly, some CEOs of banks in Nigeria have been involved in financial scandal the case of default Intercontinental, Skye, PHB and Oceanic banks are perfect example. The CEO of Satyam in India was equally enmeshed in another financial scandal, and he took the final responsibility for all accounting misappropriations (Bhasin, 2015 & 2016). These have drawn the attention of regulators, policy makers, researchers, and other stakeholders in propelling the need for good corporate governance practice that ensure that the CEOs of corporate institutions are not of questionable character both in developed and developing country.

However, an effective and dynamic Chief Executive Officer (CEO) leadership and board members represent an essential ingredient in achieving and maintaining public trust as well as confidence in the running of corporate entities. An effective CEO ensures that the operation of a corporate entity complied with the highest standard of corporate governance which ultimately create and deliver value to shareholders and achieve continuous corporate success and existence. The CEO is also in charge of the overall governance of a business firm and is accountable to shareholders for creating and delivering sustainable value as well as ensuring long term profitability.

In recent time, researchers in the field of corporate governance and corporate financial reporting began to link the influence of CEO dynamisms, most typically ownership, gender diversity, and reputation on firm value. However, the extent to which this CEO dynamisms influences firm value remained an unresolved empirical question. A common argument by these scholars is in the fact that dynamisms improve the quality of decisions of the board as well as enhancing its monitoring roles. Dynamisms can improve the quality of decisions of board as well as enhancing its monitoring roles in that, diverse set of people are not likely to be hard in terms of decision making and more diverse group are expected to engage in high quality analysis. According to Kosnic (1990), diversity among board member backgrounds may promote the airing of different perspectives and reduce the probability of complacency and narrow mindedness in a boards' evaluation of executive proposals. This is in line with the view that a wide range of solutions to strategic corporate problems can be achieved when a diverse board is in place. Another argument is that improved information access and its detailed evaluation may be achieved through racial diversity of board members.

This study has been largely motivated by finance literature that have bordered on chief executive officers (CEOs) attributes on firm (Assenga, et al., 2016; Ghardallou, et al., 2020; Hamidlal and Harymawan, 2021; Mukherjee and Sen 2021). These studies have been able to document that the attributes of the CEOs have impact on financial performance. We intend to advance this path by investigate the extent to which CEOs dynamics effect firms value. Is CEO Ownership significantly influence the value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria? Do CEO Gender Diversity significantly affect the value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria? Is CEO Reputation significantly influencing the value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria? With the progressive debate and agitations on whether CEOs characteristics impact on firm performance, thus does this comes as mere representation or does it translate a better

and material increase on the value of firms. Hence, it is of pivotal interest to know whether the CEOs dynamics really have effect on the value of firm. Thus, this is the consideration of this study.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram

Theoretical Framework

Corporate monitoring by diverse board is expected to constrain managers' behaviour because the board may influence managers to pay more attention on firm value and much less on opportunistic behaviour. It is therefore, assumed that if CEO dynamism increases monitoring, it could be linked with increased value of the banks.

Agency theory views CEOs in corporations as an agent of the owners. Therefore, it is expected that the CEOs will put the best interest of the owners above their own. In acting for the best interest of the owners, the CEO will strive to increase the value of the banks in which they serve because the agency theory view managers as a commercial stitution that mitigates problems and safeguard the shareholders wealth (Hermalin & Weisbach, 2003). When the CEOs is well diverse in its characteristics through their ownership, gender and reputation in the society, it is expected to add to the way the investors and potential investors perceive the banks which could shape the investment decision of existing shareholders and potential ones and hence increase the value of the banks.

Another important theory to underpin this study is the upper echelon theory. The theory of upper echelon posits that firms who wish to attract, retain, and benefit from different talents should enhance the top management with CEOs of diverse characteristics (Gelfand, et al 2004). It was concluded that when the top management is diverse, it helps in sending signal to employees about possible advancement potentials and the sensitivity of the senior management team. Therefore, firms with diverse top management are believed to play a significant role in enhancing the value of the firms. Also, it is believed that the features of upper echelon of an organization could influence the practices adopted and decisions made by an organization (Hambrick & Mason, 1984).

Oppong (2014) posited that there is reason to believe that establishments parallel the profile of the dominant persons who govern the activities of the organization and that some organizational pathologies may reflect pathologies in the character of these dominant individuals. Their perceptions of the corporate environment can be said to determine to a large extent how business units act in response to their environment. Thus, the organizations are what their leaders think, feel, perceive, and believe. Thus, according to upper echelons theory, managerial characteristics affect firm value and performance, either directly or mediated by organizational outcomes (Hambrick and Mason 1984).

Upper echelons theory is founded on these fundamental principles: that organizational outcome – both strategies and effectiveness – are reflections of the values and cognitive bases of powerful actors (senior executives) in the organization (Carpenter, et al, 2004; Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Empirical research that followed the theory of

Hambrick and Mason suggested that the top management team (TMT), most especially the CEO matters to organizational firm value and performance. Bantel and Jackson (1989) and Murray (1989) documented that top management team demographics related to innovation, firm value and performance respectively. Leadership researchers have associated behavioral characteristics with firm value and performance (Waldman, Ramirez, House & Puranam, 2001). More specifically, the theory states that top managers' perception of their corporate environment influences the strategic choices they make which eventually affects the performance and the value of the organization. In other words, personal characteristics of top managers determine the aspects of the environment that they can see and what they see inform the decisions they make regarding strategic choices which ultimately affects the bottom-line of the organization. In view of this, the study adopted the upper echelon theory to underpin the study of CEO dynamisms and firm value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria and supported by agency theory.

Prior Research and Hypothesis Development

Chief Executive Officer Ownership and Value of Firm

Wu and Dong (2020) investigated how a change in CEO ownership influences financial performance and market return in the long run. Using an accounting-based framework, they measure financial performance and changes in CEO ownership by using the public firms in the Taiwan Stock Exchange from 1996 to 2018. The findings in CEO ownership are consistent with the convergence-of-interests, entrenchment, and signaling hypotheses in different empirical tests. The study found a positive relation between return on assets (ROA) and changes in CEO ownership when the CEO ownership is decreasing. In contrast, ROA is negative significantly associated with CEO ownership when the CEO ownership is increasing. Moreover, the study also found that market performance is significantly positively associated with CEO ownership, which is consistent with the signaling hypothesis.

Page (2011) estimated a dynamic model in which a board of directors and a CEO interact to set the levels of CEO incentives and effort. The intent is to understand the effort that CEO incentives have on firm value. In the model incentive levels are the result of CEO risk aversion, the cost of CEO effort, the effort of CEO effort on firm value, the volatility of shocks to firm value, and the preference a board has over giving a CEO equity ownership. Model estimates show that CEO effort is an important component of firm value, and that CEO is exerting a substantial amount of effort, on average 94.7% of the possible maximum. A one percentage point increase in CEO ownership is found to increase firm value 7.6 basis points, with the net (of the increase in CEO ownership) benefit to shareholders being 4.6 basis points.

Tan, et al (2001) examined the effect of CEO ownership on firm performance. The findings suggest that CEO ownership and firm performance are jointly determined. Firm performance affects CEO ownership positively and in turn, CEO ownership has a positive effect on firm performance. Our results also show that firms managed by founder CEOs have better performance and that the CEO duality structure is beneficial in a turbulent environment.

Griffith (1999) examined the hypothesis that the amount of CEO ownership has a dominating effect on the value of the firm. Using a diverse sample of firms, firm value as measured by Tobin's q is found to be a nonmonotonic function of CEO ownership. Specifically, Tobin's q rises when the CEO owns between 0 and 15% and declines as CEO ownership increases to 50%. Beyond 50%, the value starts to rise. Firm value also is found not to be a function of management ownership when CEO ownership is separated out, indicating that CEO ownership does have a dominating effect on firm value.

Roman (Undated) examined the relationship between CEO ownership and firm performance after the CEO resignation. The study researches this on a large sample of North American companies. The results of the main regressions show that firm performance after the CEO resignation is unrelated to CEO ownership before the CEO resignation. This is the case when performance is measured as a firm's Tobin's q , MVA, EVA, ROA, ROE and ROS. The conclusion of this study is therefore that CEO ownership does not lead to an improvement of firm performance of the period after the CEO has resigned.

Law and Ningnan (2021) investigated the effect of individual chief executive officers' (CEOs') characteristics on corporate performance. CEOs across 50 Chinese firms over time were selected and it was discovered that CEOs' specific factors play a significant role in their firms' performance. CEOs' demographic characteristics include their

legal background, dual position (that is, as both CEO and chairman of the same firm), shareholding ratio, gender, and tenure. The findings show that CEOs with a legal background have a positive influence on return on assets. Robustness tests support the validity of the main results. Our findings are consistent with the human capital theory and provide support for human-capital explanations in which CEOs' legal expertise enhances their performance and corporate governance.

Altarawneh, et al (2020) reviewed existing literature related to the different facets of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) that may add value to firms. The focus was on CEO characteristics as the CEO position is very crucial in the management hierarchy, CEOs become part of the important factor that enhances the firms' performances as well as financial reporting quality, and their characteristics are claimed to play essential roles in the firms. Many firms have excelled in business as a result of their CEO's characteristics. However, prior studies have manifested mixed and inconclusive results as well as several gaps in the literature have also been identified due to the inconsistent results of previous studies. In addition, previous research highlights the individual CEO's characteristics that impact the firm's performance and also the quality of financial reporting and provides an impetus for conducting more studies in related areas.

Vintila and Gherghina (2021) examined the impact of corporate governance mechanisms and CEO characteristics on U.S. listed companies' performance. The corporate governance mechanisms are: shareholdings of insiders, shareholdings of the institutional investors and mutual funds, board size and the number of independent directors in the board. The study used Tobin's Q, return on assets, return on equity, price to book value and price earnings ratio as performance measures. Additionally, the study considered the impact of CEOs characteristics on companies' performance. These characteristics were: CEO status regarding the possibility of holding multiple functions, the CEO's possibility of being the founder of the company that he manages, state of residence, age and tenure in CEO position. The study also controlled for firm size, firm age and gearing. Their findings suggest mixed results between corporate governance and firm performance.

Silvina, et al (2021) examined the impact of CEO Education on Firm Performance. The sample covers 180 observations from IDX LQ45 listed on Indonesia Stock Exchange for period 2017 until 2020. The CEO Education is defined by the field of study in economic, management, business, or accounting. Firm Performance is measured by Tobin's Q from market-based perspective. Board characteristics and Stock Returns are used as control variables in this paper. The result shows that there's a relationship between CEO Education and Firm Performance. CEO with economic, management, business, or accounting background have a positive and significant impacts on Firm Performance. The result becomes stronger with additional test of CEO Education measured by the level and quality of education on Firm Performance, supporting that CEO Education does enhance the Firm Performance.

Chief Executive Officer Gender and Value of Firm

Vintilă, et al (2015) investigated the influence of characteristics of the corporate board and chief executive officer (CEO) on firm value, using a sample of companies listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange from 2007 to 2011. The study considered board independence, committees, size, and diversity as board characteristics, as well as CEO characteristics such as CEO age, tenure, dual roles of CEO and chairman, country of residence, and gender. It employed the Tobin's Q ratio as a proxy for firm value. Findings revealed that board size negatively influences firm value, whereas curvilinear relationships are found among board independence, diversity, and firm value. Also, CEO tenure positively influences firm value, whereas the other governance variables are not statistically significant.

Chia-Hsien, et al (2020) explored whether various characteristics of chief executive officers (CEO) enhance the impact of CEO overconfidence on a firm's value after mergers and acquisitions. The study finds that overconfident CEOs have a positive impact on firm value after mergers and acquisitions. The study also shows that overconfidence amongst CEOs can help to explain merger and acquisition decisions and the likelihood of pursuing acquisitions. Young CEOs were also found to significantly increase the impact of CEO overconfidence on a firm's value after mergers and acquisitions, while female CEOs were found to be more risk averse when compared to their male peers, with lower leverage and less volatility in their firms when compared to firms run by male CEOs.

Nguyen, et al (2021) conducted with the goal of determining the influence of CEO characteristics, including CEO experience, on the financial leverage of listed companies in Vietnam. Financial leverage is among the vital financial policies for any business. A review of upper echelons theory suggests direct influence of CEO characteristics on

setting business policy and inevitably on firm financial leverage. The study conducted generalized method of moments regression. The data studied consist of 770 observations on 110 companies listed on Vietnam's two major stock exchanges, Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange (HOSE) and Hanoi Stock Exchange (HNX), over the period 2012–2018. It was found that CEO experience, CEO education, and CEO gender are significantly positively correlated with firm leverage whereas CEO age is negatively correlated. Their results also provide additional useful information for shareholders and investors in recruiting a new CEO or balancing CEO power in the business.

D'Ewart (2014) investigated the academic conclusions on how CEO gender and salary affect firm value, while at the same time adding data on how CEO age affects firm value. Via an event study of S& P 500 CEO changes from 2000 to 2006, the study confirms the current academic findings and discover that CEOs promoted during their 40s negatively influence firm value, while CEOs in older age brackets show a positive abnormal return on firm value. With this validation and addition to the existing data, firms and investors can more effectively assess proper candidates for the position of CEO and allocate resources accordingly

Diks (2016) examined impact of CEO characteristics on firm value. Does CEO's age, compensation, tenure, or gender influence Tobin's Q? The sample consists of 483 CEOs who are in charge of firms on the S& P 500 during the period 2000 till 2015. Through a linear regression and a fixed effects model, results show that CEOs do have significant impact on firm value. So, companies should consider the characteristics of their candidates before hiring a new CEO.

Saidu (2019) examined the impact of the chief executive officer's (CEO) ownership, education and origin on firm performance. The study uses balanced panel data for 6 years from 2011 to 2016 to run ordinary least square regression. The study uses a sample from firms in the financial sector listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2011 to 2016. The findings indicate that CEO education improves profitability. Similarly, stock performance gets improved when the CEO has prior experience of the firm before being appointed as the chief executive officer.

Recently, gender diversity is more discussed in literature and in political systems. First of all, Europe started to set a quota which requires a certain percentage of women in the board of directors. They argue that females need to get the chance to fulfill managerial roles within the company and board. The United States lags behind Europe in this topic and has lower gender diversity in boards. Carter, D'Souza, Simkins, and Simpson (2010) argue that competent women and ethnic minorities should have the opportunity to participate in the board of directors and upper management. They possess external networks, information, and other characteristics

Hamidlal and Harymawan (2021) examined the relationship between the CEO power and firm value of non-financial companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2014–2018 periods. The samples are 322 observations and selected through purposive sampling method. Data was analyzed using multiple linear analysis methods. The results uncovered that ownership power; expert power and prestige power have a positive relationship with firm value. The most probable reasons could be that CEO share ownership encourages better decision-making process that contribute to enhanced corporate value. A longer tenure as a CEO signals high professionalism and expertise of the CEO that led to improved decision quality made by the CEO.

Ghardallou, et al (2020) investigated the impact of chief executive officer's (CEO) attributes on firms' performance. Specifically, it examines the influence of CEOs' education, professional experience, tenure and gender on Saudi firms' performance. The study looked at a sample of 120 listed firms on Tadawul stock exchange from 2014 to 2017. Data on financial and accounting variables are obtained from the annual reports of the selected companies. The study used a panel model and formulates three different equations using the GMM estimator. Findings prove that CEO educational background does matter. In particular, companies employing CEOs with business administration, economics, finance, or accounting degree will perform outstandingly better. Similarly, stock performance gets improved when the CEO has a postgraduate qualification, i.e., when the CEO holds an MBA, a master, or a PhD degree. Besides, results reveal that executives who have an experience in a related field will positively affect the firm's performance. Finally, evidence shows that high CEOs tenure improves corporate performance.

Marimuthu, et al (2009) investigated the influence of demographic diversity of boards on performance of firms. Non-financial listed companies were used as sample and data were obtained from secondary sources for the period 2000 to 2006. OLS regression was used on cross-sectional data. Based on the findings, gender and ethnic diversity have positive but weak effect on firm financial performance. Ilogho (2017) investigated the impact of nationality of board

members and ethnicity on performance of firms quoted on NSE. Data from 60 non-financial firms covering 2012-2015 were utilized and Ordinary Least Squares regression method was employed. The result indicated insignificant influence of ethnicity on performance of the sampled firms.

Chuah and Hooy (2018) carried out an investigation to ascertain empirically whether or not the ethnic diversity of board affect performance of firms. The directors' details were hand-collected through identifying them as their individual ethnicity. Panel data methodology was utilized by the authors. The result revealed a significant positive influence of ethnic diversity on performance of the firms during the study period. But this is possible only if majority of the board members comprised of independent directors. Using data from secondary sources, Marimuthu (2008) examined empirically whether diverse ethnicity of top-level management affect performance of the sample firms. The study period was 2000-2005. OLS was utilized as technique of analysis. The finding shows that ethnic diversity led to superior financial performance.

Cheong and Sinnakkannu (2014) examined the influence of ethnic diversity of board, board members' ethnicity and market, as well as measures of book on performance of firms using data from Malaysian stock market. The study controls for firm as well as characteristics of board. The result revealed that ethnic diversity positively and significantly influenced performance of the firms during the study period. Ujunwa, et al (2012) examined empirically how board attributes affect performance of firms listed on NSE. The study utilized the random and fixed-effects generalized least squares regression. Secondary source of data was utilized to obtained data for the sample 122 firms from 1991 through 2008. The findings showed that size of the board and diversity in gender negatively influenced performance of the firms. On the other hand, board ethnicity was found to have positive impact on firm performance.

Assenga, et al (2016) carried out an investigation to determine empirically whether or not board attributes influence performance of firms listed in Tanzania. The sample comprised of 80 firm-years observations covering 2006-2013. Data were obtained from annual reports and accounts of the sample firms. The findings showed a positive statistical influence of diversity of gender on the performance of the firms during the study period. Further, the result revealed an insignificant effect of size of the board on performance.

Chief Executive Officer Reputation and Value of Firm

Muien, et al (2021) explored the influence of CEO Reputation on the Company Financial Distress. The population of the study was all non-financial companies that are listed on the Pakistan stock exchange (PSX). The final sample size was 285 companies that cover the period from 2006 to 2017. CEO reputation plays important role in predicting financial distress. Based on the upper echelon theory, CEOs can influence in a company decision making, value creation and financial reporting decisions based on their specific skills, reputation and personal characteristics.

Mukherjee and Sen (2021) investigated the impact of CEO attributes on corporate reputation, financial performance, and corporate sustainable growth in India. Using static panel data methodology for a sample of NSE listed leading 138 non-financial companies over the time-frame 2011 to 2018. The study found that female CEOs and CEO remuneration are associated with corporate financial performance positively, whereas CEO busyness, as expected, holds a significant negative relationship with corporate financial performance. Moreover, the results demonstrate that CEO age is associated with corporate sustainable growth negatively, while tenure appears to have a significant and positive association with corporate sustainable growth.

Garay, et al (2007) using a sample of Venezuelan Banks during systemic crises, it was found that outside directorship of CEOs is negatively affected by banks' performance, measured by their default risk. Their result suggested that personal monitoring talents are what is being purchased when CEOs are appointed as outside directors. In addition, the negative effect of firms' performances on their CEO reputation is significantly stronger in an emerging market, suggesting that CEO reputation helps to control for managerial agency costs when other governance mechanisms are absent.

Cianci and Kaplan (2010) made two experiments in which MBA students make judgments about a company's future performance and management's reputation after the company reports poor financial results. Information about the CEO's pre-existing reputation is manipulated at three levels (favorable, unfavorable, or none) and the plausibility of management's explanation is manipulated at two levels (plausible or implausible). Generally, the results indicate that management's explanations influence investors' judgments of the company's future performance and that

judgment about management were jointly influenced by both manipulated factors. Specifically, our results indicate that a pre-existing favorable management reputation is an enduring trait that is not damaged even when management offers an implausible explanation. The study also found that judgments about management's intentions for explaining poor performance represent a partial mediator for judgments about management's reputation. In the light of the above, we hypothesize in null for that:

- Ho₁: CEO Ownership does not significantly influence value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- Ho₂: CEO Gender does not significantly influence the value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.
- Ho₃: CEO Reputation does not significantly influence the value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Methodology

Data Collection Method, Population and Sample

Secondary data source was utilized and obtained from the Banks' annual reports and accounts from 2012 - 2021. The period selected is considered important because it coincides with the period of continuous clamor for dynamism in board leadership and improved value and financial performance.

The study population covers eighteen (18) Commercial Banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at December 31, 2021 and a sample size Sixteen (16) Commercial Banks were used for the analysis out of eighteen that were quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group as at 31st December, 2021. Convenient sampling techniques were used to arrive at the sample size of the study which is sixteen listed Commercial Banks.

Research Technique and Model Specification

Robust Ordinary Least Square was employed for the analysis having satisfied some of the key assumptions such as heteroskedasticity, multicollinearity and normality test of the standard error. The choice of this is due to the fact that Ordinary Least Square is regarded as best linear unbiased estimator.

The following equation forms the model of the study using balanced panel multiple regression.

$$EPS_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 COW_{it} + \beta_2 CGD_{it} + \beta_3 CRP_{it} + \beta_4 LVR + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

EPS = Earnings per share, COW = CEO ownership, CGD = CEO gender diversity, CRP = CEO reputation, LVR = Leverage, $\beta_1, - \beta_4$ = Coefficient of explanatory variables, β_0 = Constant, μ = Error Term and it = Banks and Time.

Description of Variable

Variables	Proxy (ies)	Measurement
Value of Firm	Earnings Per Share	Earnings per share was measured using ratio of profit after tax to number of common stock outstanding
Board Dynamism	Board Ownership	Value of share owned by CEO of banks over the total value of shares (Farouk, 2018)
Board Dynamism	CEO Gender Diversity	One (1) is allocated where a bank has female CEO and otherwise zero (0) value is assigned (Parveen, Malik, Mahmood & Ali Jan, 2016).
Board Dynamism	Board Reputation	Value of one is assigned to a CEO with national honours such as GCFR, CFR, GCON, OFR, MFR, MON and OON and Zero if otherwise (Authors' Measurement)
Control Variable	Leverage	Total debt divided by total assets of the banks (Farouk, 2018).

Source: Author Compilation, 2023

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Presentation

The descriptive statistics is presented in Table 1. The table showed the minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation and normality test showcased through skewness and kurtosis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	Variables	Min	Max	Mean	Std.
J/Bera	S/Wilk				
0.0012	EPS	0.18	4.67	1.52	1.10
	0.00000				
0.0000	COW	1.01	9.96	4.18	2.45
	0.00000				
0.0000	CGD	0	1	0.19	0.39
	0.00016				
0.0000	CRP	0	1	0.50	0.50
	1.00000				
0.0000	LVR	50.3	97.2	83.9	6.54
	0.00000				

Source: Descriptive Statistic Results Using STATA 13

*Skew = Min = Minimum, Max = Maximum, Std = Standard deviation, Skewness, Kurt = Kurtosis

Table 1 indicates that the smallest value for earnings per share is 0.18 implying that the lowest value for earnings per share within the banks for the period covered is at 18 kobo, while the highest value for the same period stood at 4.67. This means that the maximum amount recorded by banks for earnings per share is ₦4.67k. On the average each banks earns at least about ₦2.

The lowest level of CEO ownership was 1%, while the highest value of CEO ownership stood at 9.96%. On average, the shares held by the CEO of banks within the study period stood at 4% of the entire shares. For CEO gender diversity, the minimum value recorded is zero, while the highest is five. This means that there were banks CEO that was not a woman during the study period, while the highest number of women recorded for any bank is 1, while on the average, most banks' have more of male CEO than a female CEO on their board based on the mean value which is far less than one. CEO reputation has the smallest value of 0 and largest value of 1. The mean value of 0.50 which implies that, on average, half of the banks CEOs had national honor which stand as reputation for them.

Data Analysis

Table 2 shows the Spearman correlation of the variables of the study. It also displays the association among the independent variables themselves.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	EPS	COW	CGD	CRP	LVR
EPS	1				
COW	.1393	1			
CGD	.2163*	-.0835	1		
CRP	.1948*	.0085	.3953*	1	
LVR	-.0413	-.0620	-.1649*	-.0796	1

Source: Correlation Matrix Results Using STATA 13

*. Correlation is significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Earnings per share are positively but weakly correlated with CEO ownership and leverage used as control variable. These indicate that the variables move in the same direction but not too significant. Also, the correlation between CEO gender diversity, CEO reputation and earnings per share are significant and positive implying same direction relationship. The relationships amongst the independent variables were most insignificant and negative except for

one that was significantly associated (CEO gender diversity and CEO reputation). Therefore, to establish the presence of multicollinearity among the independent variables, multicollinearity test was conducted by estimating the Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The values from the result indicated absence of multicollinearity. To validate this position, the mean VIF of 1.11 further showcase that multicollinearity is tolerably mild.

Hypotheses Testing

The section presents and discusses the regression result. This is followed with interpretation, and analysis of the findings.

Table 3: Summary of Regression Results (Robust OLS)

	Variables	Coeff	T-Stat	Prob	Cum. R
Constant	0.3736	0.33	0.739		
COW	0.0654	1.98	0.049		
CGD	0.6270	2.67	0.008		
CRP	0.2396	1.31	0.192		
LVR	0.0073	0.57	0.572		
	R ²				0.0985
	Adjusted R ²				0.0753
	F-Statistics				4.23
	P-Value				0.0028

Source: Result output from Stata 13

*Coeff = Coefficient, Stat = Statistics, Prob = Probability, Cum. R = Cumulative Result

Cummulatively, the R² of 0.0985 (9%) shows the extent to which the value of firm is explained by CEO ownership, CEO gender diversity, CEO reputation and leverage. Also, the F-statistic test value of 4.23 shows that the study model is fitted and the relationship between the two extreme variables are not due to mere occurrence.

The findings revealed a positive and significant influence of CEO ownership on value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This implies that having more ownership interest by the bank CEO adds value to the banks and brings about positive effect on the performance. This finding is in contrast with the studies of Roman (Undated), while that of Wu and Dong (2020), Page (2011), Tan, Chng and Tan (2001), Griffith (1999) concur with our finding. The study, therefore, reject the null hypothesis one of the studies which posited that CEO ownership has no significant effect on value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

The regression results revealed a positive statistically significant relationship between CEO gender diversity and value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria for the period investigated. This means that an increase in the numbers of women CEO of banks improves their value and hence the level of financial performance. This result may imply that increasing the number of female CEO could increase the board's monitoring since women are more inquisitive than male directors. The finding is in line with those of Chuah and Hooy (2018), Assenga, Aly and Hussainey (2016) and Cheong and Sinnakkannu (2014) but contrary to that of Naseem, et al (2017) and Ujunwa, et al (2012). From the foregoing discussion, this provides evidence of rejecting null hypothesis two of the study which states that CEO gender diversity has no significant effect on value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Board reputation has a positive but insignificant impact on value of listed commercial banks in Nigeria which implies that more numbers of CEO with national honour enhances the value of the banks and hence increases their financial performance insignificantly. This finding may not be surprising as the banks' CEOs with national honours were few within the study period. As such their positive impact on value of the banks may not be felt significantly. Based on this, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis which states that CEO reputation has no significant effect on value of listed Commercial Banks in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

From the regression results, it is found that CEO dynamisms significantly influenced the value of commercial banks in Nigeria during the period under study. Individual result indicated that the influence of CEO ownership, CEO gender diversity and value of commercial banks were positive and significant. Board reputation was however found to have positive but insignificant influence on value of commercial bank in Nigeria.

The results and outcomes from this paper have theoretical, practical, and regulatory implications. The findings suggest a constant need for CBN to enforce and urge banks to fully comply with corporate governance and ensure dynamism of the CEO for guaranteeing their improved value and financial performance.

Furthermore, there is need for management to consider reputations of CEOs before their appointment into the board of banks. Finally, the finding has reinforced the upper echelon theory which is built and advocates diversity in top management of organization to ensure organizational success.

Conclusion

Emanating from the analysis conducted, it is concluded that diversity in banks is essential for achieving better inputs from varieties of dynamic and seasoned directors to guaranteed and enhanced the earning.

Recommendation

It is therefore recommended that in order to boost and ensure continuous improvement of earnings of commercial banks in Nigeria. The management should ensure that the bank board cut across three major ethnic groups in Nigeria and people with national honours should be considered. Furthermore, appointment of women to the banks board should be part of the cardinal point to be considered during appointment of directors of banks.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study has contributed to knowledge in many ways. First, is on the selection of the variables and their measurement uniqueness from previous research. Second is the study period which is considered current and must have addressed changes in recent time affecting the previous data used by other studies. Thirdly, the study concentrated on only the banking sector which is a key driver of Nigeria economy. And lastly, the choice of the model used as proxy for value of firm which is the most fit for financial sector.

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